

The *Pokémon Go* Phenomenon

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At CoolJapan.es, we couldn't pass up the opportunity to discuss what became a true mass phenomenon in the video game market: *Pokémon Go*. Join us to discover more details about this curious augmented reality game.

This mobile game, centred on catching, raising, and training creatures, has been a huge success, and in July 2026 it will celebrate no less than ten years. While *Pokémon* had a canonical release for Nintendo 3DS in 2016—*Pokémon Sun* and *Moon*—*Pokémon Go* had already surpassed one hundred million downloads on Google and Apple's app stores shortly after its release.

Although it has faced the typical decline in active users after a few years, this is normal for applications that become a trend; even so, *Pokémon Go* continues to be hugely successful, still boasting between 90 and 115 million active users in 2025. Considering that *Pokémon Go* can be played entirely for free—you don't need to pay to acquire or use it, except optionally via microtransactions—it has continued to surprise us ever since its launch in 2016.

Pokémon Go has become one of the most famous mobile applications

It all began when Nintendo suggested its development—drawing from its experience with the game *Ingress*—to the developer Niantic, formerly part of the tech giant Google. Niantic was a start-up specialising in mobile games and the use of augmented reality (AR), which combines images of the real world captured by a device's camera with in-game images, creating a mixed, real-time 3D environment that blends reality with fiction.

This type of technology is easy to recall, as it was also used on the Nintendo 3DS, which came with various AR cards for gameplay.

Niantic's most notable early success was the game *Ingress*, initially accessible by invitation only. Later, it entered open beta, and could be enjoyed not just on Android devices but also on iOS. *Ingress* allowed players to choose between two factions, the Resistance and the Enlightened.

This game—just as *Pokémon Go* would do—made use of the device's GPS to allow players to control portals on a real-world map by physically moving to their locations and taking them from the opposing team.

The idea was then applied to Pokémon, based on this novel concept, which helped propel *Pokémon Go* to success. Pokémon was already one of the most recognisable franchises in gaming history, and this extra boost was what made *Pokémon Go* take off so spectacularly.

Walking around the real world to encounter Pokémon in different locations is a dream come true for many players since childhood, and it also attracted people outside the Nintendo franchise. Niantic didn't have to make too many adjustments, as the core mechanics of *Pokémon Go* were similar enough to *Ingress*.

Instead of two teams, in *Pokémon Go* players could choose from three factions from day one: Team Valor, Team Instinct, and Team Mystic, associated with the three Legendary Birds of the original Green (Blue outside Japan) and Red editions—Moltres, Zapdos, and Articuno—led by Candela, Blanche, and Spark, assistants to Professor Willow, who acts as the “Pokémon Professor” for this release, guiding and mentoring the players.

Here, the leaders of the different teams that *Pokémon Go* players can choose during their adventure

Players roam the real world with the GPS —Global Positioning System— on their mobile device activated, and suddenly, a Pokémon may appear nearby. To catch it, they must walk to the location shown on their device’s screen. Once there, they can capture it using Pokéballs, which in the game are replenished by visiting the various PokéStops — places where in-game items can be obtained— often located near real-world monuments, street art, and similar points of interest.

Many businesses, even local ones, found ways to benefit from *Pokémon Go*. There are numerous routes for hunting Pokémon, bars taking advantage of nearby spawns, and some establishments even offering discounts to *Pokémon Go* players.

Pokémon Gyms can also be found around the world —for example, in police stations, gyms, parks, monuments, and churches, although not always perfectly chosen— where players can face the Gym Leader —another player— either to train or to take over the Gym for their team, one of the three available teams. Players can also defend a Gym from rivals attempting to claim it for their own team.

When a leader is defeated, a Pokémon must be left behind to defend the Gym, which also grants in-game benefits such as coins to the player who leaves a defending Pokémon. Niantic even implemented a PvP system —Player Versus Player— allowing users to have their Pokémon battle each other in the traditional way —simply meeting in person and making their Pokémon fight.

Nintendo considered everything and even released accessories to play this game alongside a mobile device: Pokémon Go Plus —and, years later, Pokémon Go Plus +— a gadget that can be worn as a pin or bracelet, allowing players not to constantly watch their phone or tablet screen. This device works in conjunction with the game and will emit a sound, for example, when approaching a wild Pokémon.

On the left, Junichi Masuda, producer, director, and composer throughout the Pokémon series; next to him, Tsunekazu Ishihara, producer of the Pokémon franchise and president of The Pokémon Company; alongside him, John Hanke, CEO of Niantic and creator of *Pokémon Go*; and finally, on the right, we see the ever-energetic Shigeru Miyamoto, Nintendo’s famed creative mind and “father” of many of its popular video game franchises —the most famous being Mario.

Problems Raised by *Pokémon Go*

A video game of this nature, unfortunately, also brought a number of drawbacks. Its reliance on augmented reality technology, combined with the GPS system—which, when configured for maximum accuracy, brings its own issues, such as transmitting more data and using additional bandwidth to improve location tracking and the *Pokémon Go* map—and the requirement to play while walking around the real world, has led to unusual incidents, including facilitating thefts, discovering corpses, and other unexpected events.

Additionally, some celebrities, like director Oliver Stone, expressed disapproval of *Pokémon Go* and what it represents, contributing to the game’s negative reputation among certain audiences. The application uses the user’s device as GPS, with all the risks that entails. There is also the danger of accidents while walking on the street, given how engrossing the game can be—*Pokémon Go Plus* can help mitigate this, although, of course, it ultimately depends on the user’s responsibility and common sense.

Moreover, the game heavily drains mobile device batteries and consumes a significant amount of memory—as of 2026, the app weighs over 400 MB just to download, exceeding one gigabyte once all updates are installed—and uses mobile data extensively. Some businesses have taken advantage of nearby PokéStops by offering Wi-Fi to players, so they can conserve their mobile data. All of this represents additional challenges players must consider.

Advantages of Playing *Pokémon Go*

However, knowing Nintendo’s philosophy—a company that usually promotes healthy lifestyles alongside its products, encouraging exercise and social interaction—not everything was about making money or creating inconveniences. *Pokémon Go* also demonstrates positive intentions. Nintendo is a money-making machine, but also a company concerned with providing educational games, accessible experiences, and promoting physical activity.

For example, the 3DS featured “game coins” earned by walking with the console in sleep mode, while its SpotPass technology encourages players to go out, meet new people, and play together in regular games and mini-games with Miis. *Pokémon Go* has similarly encouraged socialisation, healthier habits, and outdoor activity. It has also helped players explore cities via PokéStops, Gyms, and encounters with wild Pokémon.

This approach aligns with Nintendo’s long-standing philosophy, seen in products such as the Wii and its motion-sensitive Wiimote, and the wide range of social and sports games the company has produced. It reflects the vision of Ishihara, Miyamoto, and Pokémon creator Satoshi Tajiri, who always intended the franchise to promote social interaction—from Pokémon trading via the original Game Boy Link Cable, to battling between two players with different game editions.

Nintendo’s leveraging of mobile devices’ popularity —which has remained strong a decade after *Pokémon Go*’s launch— and its partnership with Niantic, has proven a clear success, both economically and culturally. While the game may not appear as spectacular as some childhood dreams imagined —catching Pokémon in real life being a universal wish for young fans—, it offers far more engaging experiences than a simple messaging app. The application has been controversial, but it has also inspired countless community groups and associations, fostering friendships and connecting enthusiasts with shared interests.

Left: a piece of graffiti I came across while heading to a library, which happened to be a PokéStop. Centre: my Charmander, Eufrasio —named like all my Charmanders since my very first playthrough of *Pokémon Red* as a child—. Right: the map of Málaga full of PokéStops shortly after the game’s release in July 2016.

Here at CoolJapan.es, I’d like to encourage you to try *Pokémon Go*. It’s the best way to test the “Pokémon experience” in a simple way, as a mobile phone or tablet is something very common at home, and the app is completely free —not counting its optional microtransactions, which are not necessary to enjoy the experience—. Catching Pokémon has never felt so “real” or so easy!

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Ign, Pokémon, Game Freak, Nintendo, Apple’s App Store | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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